

“It’s Time for Your Check-Up!”: Analyzing Health Messages in Doc McStuffins

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Title: “It’s Time for Your Check-Up!”: Analyzing Health Messages in Doc McStuffins

Objectives: To examine how illnesses and medical care is portrayed in the TV children’s series “Doc McStuffins” in order to better understand children’s health literacy.

Background: During childhood, environments like home, school, and media actively shape early beliefs and behaviors about illness, nutrition, hygiene, and safety. Television remains one of the most widely consumed forms of media among young children, with U.S. preschoolers watching over two hours per day on average. Doc McStuffins, a popular children’s animated series, models medical situations in age-appropriate ways and may play a role in shaping early health literacy. This study examines how the show portrays illness and medical care, addressing a gap in research on how children’s media influences health-related understanding and emotional responses.

Methods: We selected two publicly available episodes of Doc McStuffins that featured illness or medical care themes for this analysis. Two independent reviewers watched and categorized the episodes using a rubric with two categories: portrayal of illness and depiction of medical care. Independent reviewers assessed portrayal of illness by its seriousness and emotional tone, and they evaluated depiction of medical care by specific tone of care and general emotional tone. Both categories were also evaluated for medium, health language, and prominence.

Results: Coders split illness severity evenly, with 50% of portrayals showing major illnesses and 50% showing minor ones, with a positive emotional tone across both episodes. They identified a total of 11 depictions of medical care, but only 7 matched between them. A nurturing tone dominated these scenes, appearing in 71.43% of the total depictions.

Conclusions: The prominence of medical care and illness in the main plot, along with understandable health language, suggests Doc McStuffins promotes health education by normalizing healthcare interactions, which may make children more excited to engage with health information. Future research should address coder discrepancies and episode selection.

Keyword 1: Medical Representation in Media

Keyword 2: Health Education for Children

Keyword 3: Emotional Tone

Keyword 4: Children’s Television

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